

SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING GIRLS WITH VISION DEFECTS TECHNICAL TACTICAL IMPROVEMENT

Tashpulatov F. A.

Associate Professor of the Department of "Physical Culture and Sports Activities" of the Tashkent Financial Institute

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ABSTRACT

In this article, a technical tactic for girls short-distance runners with visual impairments information about improvement is given.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev physical education and sports in our country to publicize, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, especially young people creation of necessary conditions and infrastructure in international sports fields of the country is taking consistent measures to ensure proper participation. Nowadays, not only men, but also women are involved in various types of athletics is engaged in. It is the training of sports girls from childhood that creates the ground for achieving high results in sports. Walk, run, jump, throw regular world championships are held among women. Women and girls working with requires the trainer to have certain knowledge about the female body is enough. It is very important to take into account the characteristics of the female body when designing the training process is important. 100-200 m athletics races were included in the programs of the "Umid Nihollari", "Barkamol Avlod", "Universiade" sports competitions of our republic. all regional team members are regularly preparing. Yulya Tarasova, Guzal Hubbieva and our friend Sitara Hamidava are among our girls in these rounds our leading girls are defending the honor of our country at the Olympics and Asian Games. But in the development of physical condition of visually impaired short-distance runners the results of the sports shown are not satisfactory. That's why he had a visual impairment improving the physical fitness of our girls, especially for short distance runners it is necessary to develop such qualities as speed, strength, agility, endurance, and flexibility. When organizing the training process, it is desirable to develop physical fitness first of all. Therefore, the short-distance runner was visually impaired improving the physical fitness of girls is one of the current problems. Short-distance running, that is, sprinting, is one of the ancient types of athletics. puts high demands on the athlete's physical and mental aspects. Short distance running from the outside, the athlete is free, light, heavy, relaxed, strong, intense, low, high and is represented by a run of many different definitions. Running short distances the analysis of cinemagrams allows for a detailed analysis of the general scene of the movement, and consistent analysis of the recorded state of movements (angles, speed, body parts shifts)

determines whether it is a precise quantitative indicator. For short distance runners age characteristics, level of training, and the nature of the sport during training is conducted taking into account the characteristics and level of physical development. Level of physical fitness of visually impaired short-distance runners to increase running distance and various jumping exercises as a relay their physical qualities, ensuring the effectiveness of the training process develops. Ability to perform movements quickly is one of the important qualities of athletics.

Speed is only for a jumper's dip, a thrower's swing, a sprinter's run not only necessary, but also necessary for athletes who do not consider speed to be their main virtue. High the level of agility speed allows you to perform small actions more easily. For a short distance level of physical fitness of female athletes with visual impairments in running in studying the opinions and comments given by our leading scientists on improvement we conclude that speed is good for short distances without developing physical quality they said that the results could not be achieved. The above makes it possible to conclude that the whole of sprinting training the content of which is the speed that a runner is able to develop in a short distance is to train the ability to maintain the entire distance. He was visually impaired especially in the process of technical and tactical improvement of short-distance running girls selection of exercises, analysis of running technique, necessary for runners of short distances action games used in training for the development of physical quality it will be appropriate to select a set.

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